

AUTHENTIC ASSESSMENTS IN ORAL COMMUNICATION: EXPERIENCES, CHALLENGES, AND MOTIVATIONS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of this research is to explore the lived experiences, influences on pedagogical practice, and challenges encountered by teachers in implementing authentic assessments through the policy guidelines of the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum, as highlighted in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015. The study's locale was the selected public senior high school teachers in the Tagbilaran City Division. The study aimed to address three main problems: experiences of teachers in the implementation of authentic assessments, the motivational factors of authentic assessments on their pedagogical practice, and challenges they encounter in the implementation of authentic assessments. The study adopts a qualitative approach and employs a narrative perspective, utilizing the thematic analysis grounded by Braun and Clarke's Data Analysis Framework. The results revealed that authentic assessments improve students' confidence and communicative skills, at the same time transforming teachers into adaptive and reflective professionals. However, teachers encountered challenges, which include limited time, insufficient institutional support, and students' lack of motivation. Thus, the researcher concluded that authentic assessments are an avenue for teachers to develop professionally and as a means of a pedagogical tool. The study recommends continuous training, collaborative professional development, and administrative support for teachers to strengthen the implementation of authentic assessments and sustain meaningful student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Authentic Assessments, Oral Communication, Experiences of teachers in authentic assessments, Implementation of authentic assessments*

INTRODUCTION

Assessment is an important component of the teaching and learning process (Brown & Race, 2013), and it functions as an assessment tool to evaluate the learners' progress. In the Philippines, the Department of Education highlights the importance of authentic assessment through DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, titled "Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program". The policy emphasizes the utilization of a learner-centered, growth-oriented, and performance-based formative and summative assessment. This policy encourages teachers to use authentic assessments that mirror real-world situations and foster higher-order thinking skills.

According to Wiggins (1990), authentic assessment is an approach that requires the learners to demonstrate essential knowledge and skills, mainly through real-world tasks like simulations, role-playing, scientific investigation, and developing a real-world project or portfolio.

However, regardless of clear policy guidelines, a significant gap remains between these policy guidelines and the actual classroom implementation of authentic assessments. Extensive studies indicate that many teachers depend mostly on traditional assessments, such as paper-and-pencil tests, instead of integrating authentic assessment methods, such as performance tasks, portfolios, and project-based learning (Saher et al., 2022). For instance, the study of Bautista and Ching (2024) revealed that even though teachers efficiently implement authentic assessments, they still encounter difficulties such as limited resources and a lack of training, resulting in going back to the traditional assessment method.

Internationally, exact challenges were observed. According to Gulikers et al. (2004), a major reason teachers avoid implementing authentic assessments in the classroom is their lack of sufficient knowledge and training in effectively designing and implementing the assessment. Locally, Abragan et al. (2022) concluded that Filipino teachers faced obstacles and issues in implementing the K-12 curriculum, explicitly focusing on DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, such as inadequate training, resource constraints, classroom challenges, and lack of support from school management, and this affects the implementation of assessments that are relevant to the real-world contexts.

In the local context, the researcher, assigned to teach an oral communication course in senior high school at Dr. Cecilio Putong National High School, plays a significant role in preparing students for both academic and professional settings; it significantly influences a student's ability to communicate with both efficacy and effectiveness. Oral communication is a core skill requiring an authentic assessment approach that reflects real-life scenarios.

According to Cruz (2023), authentic assessments play a crucial role in the Oral Communication course, as they allow learners to apply newly acquired skills in real-world contexts, enhancing their fluency and confidence. Similarly, Ulhasanah and Zaim (2020) highlight those authentic assessments, which include role-play, simulations, and oral

interviews, that assess the learner's skills and promote active participation in the classroom setting.

Thus, the researcher recognizes the urgency of exploring the experiences of public senior high school teachers in the Tagbilaran City Division handling oral communication courses, as the senior high school teachers are directly affected by the mandate of Policy Guidelines DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015. The study aims to identify the challenges, perceived barriers, and motivational factors influencing the implementation of authentic assessment. The study seeks to provide recommendations for enhancing the application of authentic assessments in oral communication courses and to address the barriers restricting the implementation of authentic assessments in oral communication courses.

Research Questions

The study explored the implementation of authentic assessments in the Oral Communication courses of senior high school teachers.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following queries:

1. What are the experiences of public senior high school teachers in the Tagbilaran City Division regarding the implementation of authentic assessments in Oral Communication courses?
2. How do these experiences shape their pedagogical practices in the implementation of authentic assessments in Oral Communication?
3. What challenges do the public senior high school teachers in the Tagbilaran City Division face in implementing authentic assessments in Oral Communication courses?
4. What recommendation can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a qualitative approach and employed a narrative perspective to explore and understand the lived experiences of selected public senior high school teachers in the Tagbilaran City Division as they implement authentic assessments in Oral Communication courses.

The qualitative research design allowed a comprehensive exploration of teachers' experiences and challenges, providing rich and detailed descriptions that contribute to the depth of the study. Narrative research, as stated by Riessman (2008) approach investigates and interprets individuals' lived experiences by means of their narratives to closely understand and comprehend the way they acquire meaning on a certain topic. This approach involves detailed responses of the participants through interviews or written narratives. This aligned with the study's aim to identify real-world challenges and

influences that shape their pedagogical practices, beyond surface-level descriptions, to reveal a more profound meaning.

This approach allowed the researcher to gain participants' personal perspectives, meanings, and insights based on their experiences and challenges, providing a deeper understanding of the topic being studied.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in selected public senior high schools in the Tagbilaran City Division. These institutions adopt the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum mandated by the DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, and offer Oral Communication courses as a core subject at the senior high school level.

Dr. Cecilio Putong National High School is the largest secondary school in Tagbilaran City, offering Academic, Technical-Vocational, Livelihood, and GAS programs for senior high school students. Manga National High School was strategically established to cater to students living in Manga, Ubujan, Taloto, and the neighboring areas in the city, resulting in a large population of faculty, staff, and students. San Isidro National High School is recognized for its dedication to academic excellence, offering quality education to major stakeholders in San Isidro, Dao, and Tiptip.

The school was selected as the research environment due to the researcher's employment at the Tagbilaran City Division, guaranteeing accessibility and familiarity with the environment and participants, and public schools are directly affected by the mandate of the Policy Guidelines of the DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, as they are encouraged to implement the guidelines in the classroom setting.

Participants and Sampling

The participants of this study consisted of teachers assigned to teach Oral Communication at a selected public senior high school within the Tagbilaran City Division. The total number of participants was 9, and they comprised 6 from Dr. Cecilio Putong National High School, 2 from Manga National High School, and 1 from San Isidro National High School. The participants of the research study were selected using purposive sampling. Public senior high school teachers were chosen as the participants of the study due to the direct mandate of the Policy Guidelines of DepEd, in which teachers are directly affected by the mandate, encouraging them to implement authentic assessments.

The researcher considered the following criteria in selecting the participants: the participants must be licensed professional teachers. Participants must be teaching an Oral Communication course at the senior high school level and must be employed at a public school within the Tagbilaran City Division. Participants must have experience with the utilization of authentic assessments. They must have at least one year of teaching experience in the Oral Communication course and be willing to participate in an in-depth interview and provide informed consent.

Research Instrument

The primary tool of the research study was a semi-structured interview guide to gather in-depth qualitative data. The instrument was specifically developed to gather comprehensive narratives and profound insights, enabling participants to convey their lived experiences in their own terminology while simultaneously exploring essential research challenges (Cohen et al., 2002).

A semi-structured interview is a flexible method for collecting data that is used in qualitative research. This structure guarantees consistency in addressing the research questions while enabling participants to express their experiences and viewpoints. The interview guide was created after looking on a review of related literature and established policies such as DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, and previous research studies on authentic assessments such as Wiggins (1990), Gulikers et al. (2004), and Bautista & Ching (2024). The research instruments were organized into four sections to ensure alignment with the research objectives.

The first section was the Teachers' Experiences with Authentic Assessment. This section explored the background and firsthand experiences of teachers in the implementation of authentic assessments in the oral communication course. The second section was the Challenges in Implementation. This section of the research instrument explored the barriers and challenges encountered in everyday situations of the participants. The third section was the Motivational Factors. This section found out the reason the participants continue in the utilization of authentic assessments regardless of the barriers and challenges. The fourth section was the Recommendations for Improvement. This section sought beneficial ideas and suggestions of the participants for improving authentic assessment practices. The final phase of the research instrument comprised fifteen questions distributed throughout the four sections: four research questions for Teachers' Experience, four research questions for Challenges in Implementation, three research questions for Motivational Factors, four research questions for Recommendations for Improvement, and one research question for the closing question.

The research instrument commenced with simple, descriptive research questions to comprehend the participants, followed by further reflective and analytical research questions, and concluded with an open-ended question. This flow of research questions was crafted to facilitate a genuine discussion and acquire authentic responses. The experts, specifically Master Teachers, validated the interview guide using the "Checklist for Close Reading of Interview Protocol" by Milagros Castillo-Montoya, University of Connecticut- Storrs, to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. A pilot test with two senior high school teachers was conducted to help refine the interview questions. A revision was incorporated according to the feedback given.

Data Collection Procedure

Ethical Review Board clearance was obtained from the University. Transmittal letters were sent to the Schools Division Office, Principals, and Participants outlining the study's purpose and procedure before the data collection.

The primary instrument for the research study – a semi-structured interview guide - was crafted and designed in line with the research objectives, theoretical framework, and related literature. The instrument was specifically reflective, analytical, and open-ended structured interview guides. The researcher scheduled individual interviews with the selected and qualified participants. Participants were nominated through the inclusion criteria.

The interview was recorded through audio, with consent from the participants, to ensure accuracy in transcription and analysis. The researcher established a professional, respectful, and non-judgmental attitude to foster openness and honesty in the participants' responses.

Data Analysis

The data analysis process relied on the gathered data from the participants. This process allowed the exploration of emerging patterns and results regarding the teacher's experiences, challenges, and motivational factors in implementing authentic assessments in an oral communication course. The study employed Thematic Analysis based on the six-step approach developed by Braun and Clarke (2006) to systematically analyze and examine the written responses of the participants.

This approach worked well for narrative research as it allowed the researcher to determine consistent patterns, meanings, and findings that correspond to the lived experiences of the participants. The research study followed the six steps: (1) Familiarization with the Data, the researcher transcribed and systematically reviewed participants' responses. (2) Generating Initial Codes, the researcher systematically determined and highlighted significant statements, phrases, or ideas from the participant's responses. (3) Searching for Themes, the researcher commenced organizing the codes that were similar into groups that might point towards themes after coding all the data. (4) Reviewing Themes, the researcher enhanced the initial themes by comparing them along with the coded extracts, as well as the complete dataset. (5) Defining and Naming Themes, the researcher conducted an in-depth analysis of each theme to determine its scope and importance in relation to the research questions. (6) Producing the Report, the final phase organized the themes into a compelling narrative that addresses the research questions of the study. The researcher used Microsoft Excel 2019 and Microsoft Word 2019 in the coding and organization process.

RESULTS

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

	Name	Years of Teaching	Gender	Authentic Assessment Approach	Citations
1	Sophia	3	Female	Role-plays, Speeches, Case Analysis	Oral presentations and Interviews, Firdausi (2024)
2	Lara	8	Female	Role-plays, Oral Presentations, Portfolios, Culminating Activities	Group Discussion, interviews, role play, Capacete (2019)
3	Daniela	6	Female	Role-plays, Simulations, Portfolios	Discussion, role-plays, and debate Maysuroh et al. (2023)
4	Manon	9	Female	Role-plays, Interviews, Portfolios	Oral Assessments, Villaber and Gonzaga (2018)
5	Megan	1	Female	Role-plays, Dialogues, Speeches	Case Analysis, Savery and Duffy (1995)
6	Yonchae	2	Female	Skits, Group presentations, Role-play	Portfolio, Barrett (2007)
7	Rhea	7	Female	Role-plays, Oral Presentations, Simulations	Oral Assessments, Villaber and Gonzaga (2018)
8	Ray	1	Male	Role-plays, Simulations, Portfolio, Oral Presentations	Oral Assessments, Villaber and Gonzaga (2018)
9	Hope	8	Female	Role-plays, Simulations, Creative Dramatics, Portfolios	Creative Dramatics, Lee et al. (2020)

**The names shown in the table are pseudonymous and do not correspond to the real identities of the participants to ensure confidentiality and anonymity.*

The table shows that participants, however diverse their teaching experience, constantly implement an authentic assessment approach which includes role-playing, simulations, oral presentations, portfolios, group presentations, and interviews. Teaching experiences of the participants ranged from 1-9 years, implying that novice and seasoned teachers implement authentic assessment approaches in the Oral Communication class. The variety of authentic assessment approaches indicates participants' commitment to accommodating various learning styles and communication proficiency. The table shows a significant link between participants' instructional methods and scholarly-supported authentic assessment approaches cited in the literature.

Theme 1: Authentic Assessments as Real-Life Learning.

Participants consistently recognized authentic assessment as a realistic and authentic approach to assessing the students' development inside the classroom. The participants of the study associated Oral Communication with application as opposed to memorization, highlighting tasks that require performance that including role-plays, simulations, and speeches, to mirror real-world communication. Numerous participants of the study have pointed out that Oral Communication shouldn't be dependent on written assessments, as the subject course itself necessitates the students to "perform" and "speak". Authentic assessments thus function primarily as a complement to real-life communication settings where students develop and acquire fluency, clarity, and confidence.

Participant 1 asserted her claims that authentic assessments are a practical way of assessing the students. "ahh I believe it's a very practical way of ahh assessing students if they really, if they really understood the lesson, because, because it's oral communication, so you have to let them talk, because it is what is required with the CG or the com, curri-, curriculum guide". P1's response highlights that authentic assessments represent the fundamental structure of communication. Allowing students to "talk" remains not merely an academic responsibility, but a teaching approach that assesses knowledge through demonstration instead of memorization.

P2 expressed her claim that she had experienced several authentic assessments in her classroom practice. "I experience uhhh doing authentic assessment such as role-play sessions, project-based learning where they have portfolio to be evaluated by themselves, peers and the teacher, another thing is they have delivery presentation, in fact they uhhh experience doing a speech in the stage or in the podium or with the use of with or without mic, and another thing is they have also experience culminating activity in relation to the, celebration of English Month and Natural uhhh Culmination of Arts". P2 did mention several authentic assessments, such as role-plays, portfolios, and stage speeches, that demonstrate the various approaches by which learning through experience takes place in the learning process.

Also, P4 expressed her enjoyment and the students in the implementation of authentic assessments. "Ahhmm okay, ahmm almost every assessment in this subject ahmm I apply the use of ahmm role playing, so most of the time in my oral comm. subject I use role-playing as their part of their assessment and some interviews of course, and I enjoyed using this assessment, and I guess the students too as I can see the way they perform they enjoyed it and for me it's, I guess their, it is their best way of expressing themselves". P4's response affirms that authentic assessments specifically include role-plays and interviews, stimulate meaningful, engaged participation. The excitement of the teacher echoes the student's eagerness to participate, revealing that authenticity enriches both teaching and educational experiences.

P6 stated in the study that implementing authentic assessments with microphones improves students' confidence. "...it's very different when the students are using the microphone when they are talking in front, somehow they are having this confidence and the superiority, while they are talking...". P6's response points out the crucial role of authenticity in implementing an assessment. Utilization of microphones and stage-like venues transforms classroom limits into an authentic communication experience. It can be viewed as a hands-on learning opportunity that improves language and social development while building an attitude of professionalism and competence.

P7 also expressed that role-plays and oral presentation would attain her goal that students must speak English Communicatively. "Ahhmm I am more on role-plays and oral presentation because I have a goal that I want my students, speak English communicatively, so without any 'códigos' they should speak English". P7's response emphasizes the significance of authentic assessments as an approach to the real-life learning process, in which the students display their authentic communication skills rather than relying on notes or memorized texts.

Theme 2: Student Empowerment through Oral Performance

Participants noticed that there has been a major growth in the students' skills of communication, fluency, and confidence when implementing authentic assessment. The students typically showed shyness and fear, but gradually became comfortable and enhanced their communication skills through consistent practice and experience of implementing authentic assessments. There has been a shift from anxiety to participation. The oral activities and exercises promote the development of the students' skills in speaking, self-expression, teamwork, and social interaction among their classmates and peers.

P1 pointed out her claim that students would feel shy at first, but then learns through the process as she highlights to the students that the Oral Communication class must not utilize written tests all the time during assessment practice. "Uhhh In, In the authentic assessment ahh they're actually shy at first but, actually they eventually ahh learn to do it because, of course they don't have choice and also because I, actually explain it on very beginning that of course this is oral communication, you don't expect me to give you written test all the time" P1 believed that to be able to empower students, it must begin with shifting how they perceive learning. Her response that the Oral Communication course needs practice and engagement in communication instead of a written test highlights a shift in the direction of learning through experience.

P2 asserted that students would feel happy with their performance and that most of them applied their learning in real-life situations, such as employment in a call center that focuses on oral communication skills. "... uhhh they were uhhh happy and delighted of their performance and another thing I, I also remember that one of my student said that without my teaching ahh about oral communication they could not guarantee the perfection or the evaluation scores, in certain call center agent, uhhh work or, most of them experience specific, good result in their college entrance exams" P2's response is

evidence of empowerment that goes beyond educational limits. The student's utilization of educational experiences in professional situations exhibits authentic and useful learning.

P5 expressed her response that even though she handled all the boys' classes, they loved authentic assessments such as oral activities. "Ahhmm the, they're all boys so they love doing the task like ahmm doing the Oral Communication activities than doing the pencil and, paper and pen test, oh they love it most because whenever I say ahh "we will have to perform like this" oh they like, they love it better than, than writing" P5's response reveals that empowerment is accomplished when students are granted the opportunity to express their thoughts openly. Performance-based assessments act as an opportunity for uniqueness, confidence, and personal growth.

P8 claimed that students would feel thrilled and that first-hand experience is much better than a pen and paper test. "Ahhh... they... seem.. quite.. thrilled in a fact that, oh this is unusual that, I'm gonna have to stand in front of the class and deliver whatever, I have to deliver.. for me its.. its because, its experience wise and its's nice that they will be able to really first-hand experience, communication rather than just pen and paper test and whatsoever." P8's response displays that authentic assessments build involvement and personal engagement in the learning process.

P9 expressed her claim that authentic assessments are enjoyable and help connect students and teachers, which led to an electrifying class. "... It's very enjoyable, students readily and quickly, and spontaneously connect to you. So, it doesn't feel forced, like, it's you know, the synergy is so awesome that, that class becomes electrifying, you, you know that moment that.. when you are really in the class and they are with you and then, time stops and you know, wow, this is one of the things that I enjoy teaching, okay those moments when, when we have a connection, real connection with our students" P9's response to the interview process highlights the way authentic assessment empowers the students to effectively express their selves openly and confidently, thus transforming learning towards a collaborative and interactive experience.

Influence of Authentic Assessment on Pedagogical Practice

Theme 3: Passion and Pedagogical Commitment.

Participants displayed an immense passion and dedication in implementing authentic assessments to achieve real-world communication learning. The motivation of the participant is fueled by a genuine intention to help students develop into confident and proficient communicators, stating that "learning by doing" is among the most important methods in teaching the Oral Communication course. Many of the participants stated that, regardless of insufficient facilities, participants persistently develop creative approaches to keep up with performance-based tasks because they view their students' progression as the most notable reward. This dedication reveals that participants recognize authentic assessment, rather than just a pedagogical approach, as an essential part of their

professional reputation and advocacy for learner-centered education that relates to the 21st century needed for lifelong learning.

P7 claimed that her motivation to implement authentic assessments is her goal that students must speak English communicatively. “What really motivates me is my goal, so I have really a goal to... let my students speak English communicatively, that is really my goal, so I am doing my part as a teacher to learn, that’s the real learning of their life, aside from learning inside the walls, ahhh four walls of the classroom, so the real learning they will be bringing is how they can speak English outside” P7’s response shows a teacher’s passionate commitment to transformative learning that goes beyond academic instruction.

P3 also pointed out that authentic assessments are effective, and students find them fun while also learning. “Ahm, what keeps me motivate ahh motivated in using assess ahm authentic assessment is that I find it ahm effective especially when students ahm have fun while learning and also ahm it, like, the the assessment is not just limited to paper-pen authentic assessment, so we can, I can also see the development on students socially, and also intellectually, that’s it” P3’s statement highlights that passion in teaching is strengthened when they observe their students’ progress and enjoyment upon their experience of authentic assessments.

P5 emphasized in the study that authentic assessments, such as oral activities, are needed in this generation, and we have to prepare students to achieve success in the future. “My motivation is that it is what is needed in this kind of era, we really have to speak up, whether we like it or not, we really have to use our voices, so we have to prepare the students if we want them to rule the world, right” P5’s response reveals her profound pedagogical commitment that allows students to communicate fluently in a dynamic and interconnected global context.

P6 noted her claim that her motivation is based on empathy, highlighting that students must learn to create connections with their peers. “I am focused more in studying alone, so I want my students to learn how to deal with other people and how to dwell with different ahm attitudes of their classmates” P6’s assertion indicates a particularly humanistic perspective on education, highlighting empathy, interaction, and growth in oneself.

P1 also expressed her claim that from the beginning of her teaching career, she believed in the principle of learning by doing. “Ah, even from the start, I believe in the principle learning by doing, so it is with that kind of assessment, learning by doing like assessments that are role-playing, such as recitation ana you can really see, ahmmm, not just theories about your lesson but they can also apply through, ahhh their own action or the way they speak” P1’s statement reflects her passion for hands-on learning, pointing out a pedagogical approach that values student participation instead of a memorization approach. Her belief in the principle of “learning by doing” displays a profound pedagogical commitment to help students’ acquisition of knowledge through firsthand experience and reflection.

Theme 4: Professional Growth and Development

Participants emphasize the implementation of authentic assessment functions as an encouragement for professional growth and development. By constantly engaging with authentic assessment tasks, participants feel motivated to develop further and improve their pedagogical strategies, assessment methods, and classroom practices. The participants' experiences imply that challenges experienced in authentic assessments typically result in opportunities for reflective practice and pedagogical improvement. As participants adapt according to the demands of students' needs and contextual limitations, they develop strengthened confidence, creativity, and flexibility in teaching Oral Communication.

P9 stated her claim that DepEd should provide more support for continuous professional development. "What can DepEd do? DepEd, get lost, just kidding, DepEd, could think of real training for teachers and give in-service quality training for them, set aside a budget for equipment, set aside a budget for textbook, set aside a budget for honorarium, honorarium for.. ahh imported speakers, because DepEd is, they prefer people on DepEd so they wont need to pay ahh there are many people who are better than us outside and we don't have, budget, it's not included in the MOOE, oh so, we do it on our own, inbreeding which is bad" P9's response displays a deeper comprehension of the need for institutional support for teachers' continuous professional development and the distribution of adequate budget.

P8 asserted that school administrators should provide and send teachers to trainings and workshops, as he believed that learning never stops. "Also, the admin should... ahh sent teacher to seminars, workshops, in higher level, we know that learning doesn't end, right? It doesn't end, it never really end about learning so, maybe if teachers will be sent to seminars, workshops, like talks, maybe they could get something out from it and apply it into the... classroom scenario" P8's response emphasizes a deeper understanding of teaching as a continuous learning process that grows by means of ongoing professional development.

P4 also expressed her experiences as she claimed that number one support must be sending teachers to trainings, as she stated that even though she had years of teaching experience, she still demands training. "I guess one of which is... ah send to, of course number one send to trainings because as I can see now, based from my experience, I actually... although I've been teaching for like a decade now but I need more trainings" P4's response highlights a reflective and development-focused mindset, realizing that effective teaching requires continuous learning and adaptation.

P3 also shared the same insights that providing a seminar and workshop for teachers would allow her to learn new strategies and assessments. "Ahm.. I guess it's the same right? That they can provide seminars and workshops for teachers so that ahm our authentic assessment because maybe there are new.. right, new strategies, new assessment, authentic assessment that can, that we can apply to in our classes today"

P3's statement displays a progressive mindset on the continuous development and pedagogical innovations.

P5 asserted that having training before teaching Oral Communication would allow her to improve her teaching strategies. "Ahhm, for preparation, yes, we really have to prepare like, yes, for training I wish, I had, public speaking trainings, before getting into teaching Oral Communication class, because as you said, ay, as they said, you cannot teach what you don't have, so, what you cannot give what you don't have" P5's response embodies the essential relationship between teachers' proficiency and pedagogical authenticity. Her response, "You cannot teach what you don't have", highlights how important it is for teachers to develop both pedagogical knowledge and subject-matter confidence before assisting students in a communication-based field of study.

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Implementing Authentic Assessments

Theme 5: Structural, Logistical, and Affective Constraints

Participants pointed out challenges in the implementation of authentic assessments, such as limited class duration, inadequate facilities and learning resources, limited institutional support, and student-related constraints such as low self-confidence and motivation. Such constraints cause gaps between participants' educational goals and their actual classroom practices.

Participant 2, Sophia, expressed her experiences of the challenges, such as a slow internet connection and a lack of microphones. "I, we had a slow internet, especially also in our school I'm sorry for that, we have a few, uhmm access of the internet connection, like when we say oral communication were not only focus on the, speaking skill but we also relate it to the uhmm areas of 21st century and the same time we had also a lack of uhmm access of using microphones" P2's response indicates the existing logistical constraints that limit the effective implementation of authentic assessments in the Oral Communication course. It can be interpreted that internet connectivity and the lack of microphones constrain the integration of technology and communication tools, which is fundamental for 21st-century learning.

P1 also claimed the utilization of the speech laboratory. "Uhh, now that I am having this interview I, but ahmm I think it would be better that ah, the admin would, because we have speech lab in our, in our school and I think it would be better that we will be, we will be able to maximize the use of speech lab in oral communication classes, because that is the main point of that.. laboratory." P1's response reveals a structural constraint regarding the lack of use of school facilities, specifically the speech laboratory, which limits the effective implementation of authentic assessments in Oral Communication. This institutional gap, where resources are supposed to improve performance-based learning, isn't properly utilized to promote real-world communication engagements.

P8 shared his experience of the affective constraints among students, such as shyness and low self-confidence. "ahh not all, not all of them are good in using the language, and

aside from that they are quite shy.. and then, they would feel shy for the reason that they don't know how to speak English, they don't know how to pronounce, they might mispronounce the words, and they feel shy around with their classmates, they are not confident, so these are some of the, difficulties" P8's response emphasizes the existence of affective constraints that notably limit the students' participation in the implementation of authentic assessment. It can be perceived that students' shyness, concern about mispronunciation, and low confidence restrict their capacity to participate effectively in Oral Communication tasks.

P3 and P6 also experienced structural constraints such as limited class duration. "Okay uhmm, challenges, since uhmm authentic assessments need time especially that when you do role-playing you have to make sure that you give uhmm time for them to practice and to brainstorm, what to do, that's why ahmm time is very challenging, in authentic assessments", "one hour time is not enough so.. as well as the idea where we can't complete the whole lesson plan for one hour is very ahmm impossible." P3 and P6's response emphasizes time as a structural constraint in the implementation of authentic assessments. It can be interpreted that preparation and implementation of authentic assessments, such as role-plays or other performance-based tasks, demand adequate time for students to perform in class, collaborate, and integrate their learning experiences.

Theme 6: Institutional Support and Development for Teachers.

Participants noted the significance of administrative support, access to professional development opportunities, and the availability of instructional resources in improving their teaching approaches. Supportive educational policies, guidance, and relevant opportunities in training were considered essential for addressing instructional challenges along with improving assessment implementations. When institutions contribute to the development of teachers, they gain increased empowerment, motivation, and confidence in implementing assessment techniques in the classroom setting.

P9 stated that DepEd provides limited training and must organize more teacher improvement trainings. "In HNU (previous school), there's just any, lots of trainings, so, you grow there professionally, but in DepEd, there are limited, to some, few people, and I'm not included, so I don't have training anymore.." When asked, does the school's or administrator's support affect the use of authentic assessments in your class? She responded, "It affects, because who cares about authentic assessment anyway? Like, how about you? Have you attended a seminar about authentic assessment? No, there's no assess, ah training like that, it's always about, managing ahh what, what DepEd orders they think, ahh different programs, ah it's more on the programs curriculum development and there's, a few on the teacher, pro, improvement" P9's response stresses the vital role of institutional support and professional development to support teachers' effective implementation of authentic assessments.

P1 also experienced the same challenges. She responded to the question; How does your school's or administrator's support affect the use of authentic assessments in your class? "So far I could not see any...thing because they leave it to the teacher.... there

are classroom observations but it, it only, it is only limited to teaching ahh to like monitoring the teacher if they really attend class or have they followed the correct four A's in the classroom, but when it comes to support like "okay you'll have to do this, like all oral communication teachers should have this kind of performance task" there was really no direct or guidance from them" P1's response reveals a significant lack of institutional support and professional development, which prevents teachers from successfully implementing authentic assessments.

P6 also expressed her experiences of the challenges as she pointed out that teachers are encouraged to use authentic assessments, but the limited class duration restricts the implementation of the assessments. "So far, the school administration wants us to use the authentic assessment but, the.. the time, the one hour time is not enough so.. as well as the idea where we can't complete the whole lesson plan for one hour is very ahhmm impossible" P6's statement points out that even though teachers understand the importance of authentic assessments, their effective implementation is obstructed by inadequate institutional support, a lack of training and development, and limited time duration.

P3 claimed that the school or the administrators should give more seminars and workshops. "Like maybe the school or our administrators could somehow give us ahhh.. seminars, workshops that can make our authentic assessment ahh successful and better to ahh better implementation of that assessment" P3's response highlights the urgent need for institutional support and professional development to improve teachers' ability to implement authentic assessments effectively.

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Participants

The participants implement performance-based assessments that correspond to real-world tasks that require communication. This method aligns with DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015, which supports the goals of the performance standard that highlight the application and implementation of skills. Additionally, this supports Gulikers et al. (2004), who claim that authentic assessments demonstrate characteristics defined by their alignment with real-world performance, setting, and results.

Furthermore, the teacher's implementation of authentic assessments conveys a collective pedagogical view in constructivist learning that allows students to acquire knowledge by means of application, collaboration, and assessment. This reveals that authentic assessments are essential in the implementation of Oral Communication courses. Vygotsky (1978) argued that students obtain learning most successfully through active participation in socially important tasks guided by their teacher.

Theme 1: Authentic Assessments as Real-Life Learning

The study revealed that Authentic Assessment as Real-Life Learning reflects the way teachers transfer concepts of theory into classroom practice, providing an essential expression of their lived experiences in the implementation of authentic assessments. It was revealed in the study that teachers constantly pointed out that authentic assessments serve as an important link connecting theoretical knowledge and real-world communication context. They believe it is essential for the students to apply their lessons via tasks and activities that replicate authentic situations involving communication. For these teachers, assessment is not just about evaluation or mere grading; it incorporates facilitating the development of learners' ability to effectively communicate and adapt to different situations. The teachers further recognized authentic assessment as a bridge linking knowledge and application, promoting the development of student learning results from basic memorization to real-world communication. Instead of focusing on traditional assessments, specifically written tasks, they implement tasks that replicate real-life context, promoting collaboration between teacher and students, problem-solving, and real-world performance.

In line with Vygotsky's Constructivist Learning Theory (1978), authentic assessments incorporate learning through real-life situations, highlighting that students acquire knowledge through active participation and guided interaction.

Theme 2: Student Empowerment through Oral Performance

It was explored in the study that Student Empowerment through Oral Performance emerges from the teachers' experiences, the way classroom assessments help students to grow their confidence and express their ideas more deeply during oral assessments. Teachers responded to the interview process that authentic assessments improve student empowerment by strengthening confidence, communicative skills, and self-determination. They experienced a notable change in the students' viewpoints, particularly among the students who were formerly shy, fearful, and unwilling to express themselves. Teachers responded that as soon as students were exposed to authentic assessments that include speeches, interviews, or oral presentations, they noticed that students gradually lessen fear and would grow confidence, and acquire a feeling of fulfillment. Based on the response of the teachers, authentic assessments promote a supportive and welcoming learning atmosphere whereby all the students, regardless of their proficiency level, may participate authentically. It lets the students express their ideas, display their distinctive qualities, and apply communication skills. Teachers noted that empowerment emerges not just from the performance of the student but also through feedback, reflection, and teamwork with their peers.

This is consistent with Vygotsky's (1978), which emphasizes social learning and guided participation, in which the growth of students is further enhanced through assistance or guidance with more experienced collaborators and teachers. Additionally, this also aligns

with the conclusions of Habagat and Hermosa (2024), who imply that authentic assessment strengthens students' interest and ability to express themselves, particularly in oral communication situations.

Influence of Authentic Assessment on Pedagogical Practice

Theme 3: Passion and Pedagogical Commitment

Teachers' responses to the study have found their profound Passion and Pedagogical Commitment as essential motivators that influence their continuous implementation of authentic assessment, as their passion and commitment influenced their pedagogical methods of teaching and formed connections with their students. It can be viewed that, despite the challenges expressed by the teachers, they perceive their teaching in the Oral Communication course as a profession grounded in intention and empathy, a purpose to mold students towards confident, skilled communicators who can engage in real-world situations. Their commitment exceeds mere compliance with the curriculum standard; it reflects an honest conviction in the transforming capacity of beneficial learning experiences of authentic assessments. Their passion can be seen in their commitment to mentoring and guiding students, and continually improving their assessment techniques. Teachers view these efforts as not burdens, rather as vital extensions of their identity as professionals. As the teachers observed the progress of students, particularly the shy students, into expressive communicators, it fueled their motivation and sense of achievement.

This is consistent with Habagat and Hermosa (2024), who noted that teachers' own passion and personal engagement serve as essential factors in encouraging constant innovation and responsiveness in assessment implementation. This also aligns with Vygotsky's (1978) Constructivist Theory, such as passion serves as cognitive scaffolding, stimulating both teaching and learning by means of supportive, affective interaction. It can be perceived that the commitment of teachers indicates that authentic assessments depend not just on policy or training but also on the emotional and professional passion of teachers who view their profession as an act of purposeful reform.

Theme 4: Professional Growth and Development

The participants in the study pointed out their collective insights that continuous Professional Growth and Development influence their pedagogical practice to improve, reflect, and adapt, which allows them to foster continuous learning and facilitate the integration of innovative student-centered methods in the classroom settings. Participants suggested that teaching the Oral Communication course in the 21st century demands an ongoing knowledge of pedagogy that includes innovation, reflection, and contextual relevance. Constant learning through workshops, seminars, and collaborative partnerships enables teachers to strengthen their assessment proficiency, enhance learning design, and align assessment methods with communicative proficiency goals. The responses of participants in the study recognized their professional growth not merely as a formal requirement but as an ongoing process of self-renewal. They highlighted that

taking part in a reflective discussion and collaborative planning enhances confidence as well as skill in the effective implementation of authentic assessment. It can be perceived that continuous learning enhances adaptability, which enables teachers to effectively cope with updates to the curriculum and the diverse communication demands of students.

These findings align with the study of Sambeka et al. (2017), who revealed that authentic assessments promote pedagogical progress through inspiring reflection regarding their methods of teaching. This also coincides with Vygotsky's (1978) Constructivist Theory, professional development reflects the teacher's Zone of Proximal Development, an area in which they grow and develop by collaborative interaction, shared knowledge, and reflective practice. In this context, teachers exhibit the method of active learning they aim to instill in their students.

Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Implementing Authentic Assessments

Theme 5: Structural, Logistical, and Affective Constraints

Most of the teachers during the interview responded that, despite the educational advantage of authentic assessments, they have expressed that they frequently encounter Structural, Logistical, and Affective Constraints that restrict their implementation of authentic assessments in the Oral Communication course. It was found that teachers experience multifaceted constraints that significantly influence the implementation of authentic assessments in the classroom setting. The implementation of authentic assessment, though its pedagogical appropriateness is restricted by the ongoing challenges that prohibit its full potential in the classroom setting. It can be perceived that teachers encounter these challenges in the implementation of performance-based evaluations because of limited class hour duration, a lack of facilities, a lack of resources, and students' low confidence and motivation.

The challenges of implementing authentic assessments coincide with the findings of Zaim et al. (2017), who noted that insufficient resources and institutional support limit the teachers' competence to implement authentic and performance-based evaluations in the classroom settings. This also echoes with Amoah and Yeboah (2021), who asserted that affective factors are also a constraint for learners and affect their participation in oral communication activities. These challenges can be perceived to be evidence of a gap between educational standards and institutional realities. Regardless, it can be recognized that the teachers' continuous implementation of authentic assessments in the Oral Communication course shows their professional mentality to deliver authentic and meaningful educational opportunities regardless of the existing challenges.

Theme 6: Institutional Support and Development for Teachers

The responses of participants in the interview process reveal that the effectiveness of the implementation of authentic assessments relies not merely on pedagogical proficiency but also on the Institutional Support and Development for Teachers that fosters professional development. Based on their responses, they acknowledge the importance

of authentic assessments in promoting the student skills in communication, yet they encounter challenges, which include insufficient administrative support, lack of seminars and workshops, and limited opportunities for professional development. These systemic challenges limit their ability to implement authentic assessments.

This can be linked to the statements of Darling-Hammond and McLaughlin (2011), who noted that meaningful development demands an ongoing and collaborative professional development through institutional support. This also aligns with Koh et al. (2012), who highlighted that teachers' ability to implement authentic assessment becomes better when schools give constant training and sufficient resources. Based on the Constructivist point of view, the school functions as the macro-scaffold (Vygotsky, 1978), guiding the development, innovation, and improvement of teachers' practices in authentic assessments. Although some of the participants have responded that school-based LAC sessions and occasional seminars are useful in improving teachers' competence, they still demand professional training and workshops. With this context, it can be viewed that without this institutional support, teachers are forced to handle the challenges of authentic assessments on their own, restricting their potential for transformation in developing communicative skills and holistic learning.

Conclusions

The study's outcome shows that authentic assessment is an essential learning approach for teaching the Oral Communication course in senior high school, as it encourages real-life learning and proficiency in communication. Nevertheless, the success of the implementation is restricted by structural, logistical, and affective constraints, specifically the lack of time, accessibility to resources, institutional support, and an inconsistent level of student motivation. Teachers' passion and innovation give them motivation to continue in implementing authentic assessment, revealing that their dedication to their profession makes a difference in overcoming and dealing with challenges in the implementation of authentic assessments.

The study concludes that effective implementation of authentic assessment requires not just teacher effort but also supportive collaboration from policymakers and school administrators. Enhancing and strengthening institutional support will help the teacher provide continuous professional development, and improving facilities are essential initiatives toward establishing authentic assessment as a sustainable and meaningful approach to learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are formulated:

1. **For Oral Communication Teachers**, be consistent and incorporate authentic performer-based speaking activities in their teaching approach, as these approaches are consistent with the study's findings that these activities improve

students' communicative skills. Consistent professional development in authentic assessment design is recommended in order to ensure consistency, validity, and meaningful outcomes in learning in the Oral Communication classroom.

2. **For School Administrators**, provide sufficient resources for teachers and support teachers by setting flexible and feasible class schedules and establishing clear guidelines that allow the efficient implementation of authentic assessments. Administrators might additionally facilitate collaborative seminars or professional learning communities that support teachers in improving their assessment techniques.

3. **For DepEd**, provide readily available and continuous training programs, regardless of whether online or at the division level, that will enhance teachers' practical knowledge in the implementation of authentic assessments. The Department of Education might consider offering modest supplemental funds to help support performance-based programs in schools, guaranteeing that assessment strategies are consistent with the requirements of the curriculum and classroom settings.

4. **For Future Researchers**, conduct similar research studies throughout various strands, grade levels, or different locations to obtain a deeper and more extensive understanding of practices in the implementation of authentic assessments. Future research studies may explore the perspective of students or examine the long-term effects of authentic assessments on communication proficiency and confidence.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly adhered to the highest ethical guidelines and principles throughout its conduct. The institution's Ethics Review Committee thoroughly assessed the manuscript to ensure full compliance. The participants were provided detailed explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits to the participants of the study, and each participant was required to sign an informed consent form before participating in the research process. The study ensured that the personal information of all participants was kept confidential and anonymized in both records and reports, and participants involved in the study could withdraw at any point without any penalty or negative consequence. The study ensured that the involved participants were treated equally and fairly throughout the research process, and no participants were privileged or disadvantaged based on their responses or level of participation.

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